

A Descriptive Study To Assess The Level Of Awareness & Attitude Regarding Learning Disabilities Among Elementary School Teachers In Selected School Of Dist Dholpur Rajasthan: A Pilot Study

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Abstract

Learning disabilities are perhaps best described as unexpected, significant difficulties in academic achievement and related areas of learning and behavior. Learning disabilities in children are one of the common problems that need special attention from family, neighbors, social circles and teachers. Teachers are the first who directly interact with the children in school when they start reading, writing or learning process. Teacher plays an important role while dealing with learning disabilities children therefore teacher role is wide such as best supporter and good resources for children in school. Teachers play a big role in early diagnosis of student learning issues. So we must need to study on learning disabilities in order to identify or assess the level of awareness regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers. Therefore, learning disabilities good level of awareness & favourable Attitude of elementary school teachers will play a important role to overcome the children. The study was carried out the level of Knowledge & attitude regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers. A descriptive research design with cross sectional survey approach was used to collect data from 50 elementary school teachers at selected school of Dist Dholpur Rajasthan in Oct & Nov 2020, and using convenient sampling method. Data was collected by using level of awareness questionnaire and attitude scale. Study result revealed that the elementary school teachers have average knowledge & moderately favourable attitude towards the learning disabilities children. The Good level of awareness & favourable attitude will help the children to overcome with the learning disabilities along with medical treatment & family Support. The paper presents the sample size, Reliability & feasibility

of tool, for further main study

Keywords: Learning Disabilities, Elementary School teachers, Level of awareness,.

Introduction

Education is the fundamental right of every child. Programs on universalization of primary education are being carried out world wide.in India with the initial efforts of dist primary education program followed by Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, the elementary education is become the priority of the government. A large number of children with mild intelltual disabilities borderline intelligence & specific learning disabilities face difficulties in coping with the academic demands in schools. Such children are large in number and their difficulties are invisible which further creates problems. These are children who seems to be functioning like others peers in all aspects except academics. Teachers are puzzled as these students do not have visible disabilities, such children might have problem in their learning process. Therefore it is essential to understand the learning the learning process, how and why learning difficulties occurs. In such case early assessment & appropriate support by the teachers, family, neighbor will helped to cope with the learning disabilities.¹

However, there is a higher reported incidence of learning disabilities among people living in poverty, perhaps due to increased risk of exposure to poor nutrition, ingested and environmental toxins (e.g., lead, tobacco and alcohol) and other risk factors during early and critical stages of development.²

Learning disabilities in school age children are one of the common problems that need special attention. Teachers are the first who directly interact with the children in school when they start reading, writing or learning process. Teacher acts as a best supporter and good resources for children in school. Teachers play a big role in early diagnosis of student learning issues. So we must need to study on learning disabilities in order to identify or assess the level of awareness regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers.³

Alkhunizi Layla, Alnas Khadija, janabi Olfat 2019 A study was conducted on knowledge and attitude toward learning disabilities among primary school teachers in dammam, qatif and alkhobar cities, K.S.A the study results reveled that Primary school teachers who participated in the present study had poor Knowledge and attitude about learning disabilities.⁴

Syed Arifa,Syed Shahid Siraj 2019:- A descriptive study was conducted on “To assess the knowledge and attitude of primary school teachers regarding learning disabilities among children in selected schools of district Pulwama Kashmir”. The result of the study revealed that majority of teachers 73.3% had moderate knowledge on learning disability, There was significant association between marital status and Age of teachers and their attitude towards learning disability.⁵

Kalita Utpal 2017:- A study was conducted to investigate the attitude of primary school teachers towards inclusive education the study result revealed that most of the teachers have moderate attitude towards inclusive education, male teachers' attitude towards inclusive education is higher than the female teachers.⁶

Shukla Poorna 2015:- A study was conducted on investigate the knowledge and awareness of learning disabilities among teachers of primary schools. In this study 68 primary school teachers in 15 schools were selected based on lottery method in Haridwar region. The study results shows that low level of knowledge and awareness about learning disabilities among teachers of primary schools.⁷

Objectives:

1. To calculate the sample size for the main study.
2. To find out the reliability coefficient of various questionnaires.
3. To find the relationship between level of awareness with attitude
4. To find out the feasibility

Materials and Methods

The descriptive research design with cross sectional survey approach was used in this study. The study populations was elementary school teachers at selected schools of Dist Dholpur Rajasthan. Written permission was obtained from Chief Block Education Officer Baseri District-Dholpur Rajasthan for conducting the pilot study. Non Probability Convenient sampling technique was used to collect data from 50 elementary school teachers from selected schools of dist Dholpur Rajasthan from 26/10/2020 to 26/11/2020, after obtaining informed consent from them. The SPSS 18 version was used to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, reliability coefficient and correlation was used

Instruments:

The data was collected by using following questionnaires: demographic information of respondents, level of awareness questionnaire, Attitude Scale

1. **The demographic information** consist of following questions of Respondents i.e. age, gender, School Location, marital status, Religion, Type of School, Class being taught, Education Qualification, Years of Experience
2. **Level of Awareness questionnaire-** After reviewing the literature, a Awareness questionnaire was made by the researchers & got content validity from the experts & their suggestions were incorporated and no questions were deleted. These experts agreed for the appropriateness of the tools for the present study. The tool consisted of 27 questions. For each question wrong answer minimum score will be 0 (Zero) and

for the correct answer maximum score will be 1(one)

3. **Attitude scale** :- It consists of 40 items & have 3 Domains ie General Attitude about Learning Disabilities, Teaches Attitude in Helping Children with Learning Disabilities, Attitude about Inclusion of Children with Learning Disabilities in which has 12,16,12 Statements respectively. It is 5 point scale & For each question minimum score 1 and maximum score 5, Reverse score for the Positive Statements, Then sum up the responses in each dimension and calculate the mean.. A five points Likert scale was used for the scoring system with 1 representing "strongly agree" and 5 representing "strongly disagree". It examines attitude of elementary school teachers what is the attitude of respondents towards learning disabilities children. For all 40 items reliability coefficient varies from 0.74 to 0.96. The overall reliability of the questionnaire was 0.88

Results

Highest Percentage (44%) of respondents were in the age group of 20-35 years, most (62%) of teachers were female, 52% of respondents were working in urban area school, 67% of teachers were married & 78% were Hindu 55% were working in private schools & 52 % teachers were teaching Class 1st std to 5th Std .Most of the respondents ie 53% & majority of teachers ie 57% were having less then 10 years of experience were have B.ed qualification.

Objective -01 To calculate the sample size for the main study

Calculation of sample size: Formula:

$$\text{Sample size} = \frac{4 \times \sigma^2}{d^2}$$

Where: σ = SD, d = Absolute degree of precision

So as per the statistical calculations minimum 50 teachers were required. After checking the feasibility, the researcher had determined the sample size of 500 teachers for the generalizations of the finding of the study.

The cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.93 and 0.95 for level of awareness & attitude of elementary school teachers respectively. The reliability coefficient for all questionnaires were very high, therefore suggesting the high internal consistency of all questionnaires

Table-1 Determination of sample size

Subjects	Variable	Anticipated mean/r	Anticipated SD	Absolute degree of precision	Confidence level	Power	Estimated n(sample size)
Elementary School teachers	Lawq	25.61	5.34	4	95%	-	81
	ASC	3.36	0.22	5	95%	-	64
	Correlation (Lawq vs ASC)	0.64	-	Effect size/SD = 0.5	95%	90%	50

Key: Lawq -Level of Awareness questionnaire ASC-Attitude Scale

Objective -2 To find out the reliability coefficient of various questionnaires.

**Table-2
Mean, SD, and Cronbach alpha coefficient of Questionnaires**

Questionnaires	Mean	SD	Cronbach alpha coefficient
Level of Awareness	125.37	19.08	0.93
Attitude Scale	114.68	24.17	0.95

Table-3
Cronbach alpha coefficient item wise for level of awareness Questionnaires

Sr No	Items	Cronbach alpha coefficient
1.	The most commonly observed learning disability in children is	0.993
2.	Learning disability is more common in	0.892
3.	Usual onset of occurring reading problem in	0.895
4.	Writing disorder includes	0.903
5.	In learning disabilities, mathematical disorder is known as	0.893
6.	Major causes of learning disability are	0.895
7.	Commonly onset of reading problem occurs before age of	0.894
8.	Which is the most essential hormone for mental growth	0.878
9.	Strategy for teaching children with calculation problem is by	0.898
10.	Children with calculation problem are treated with	0.801
11.	Children who have reading/spelling problem mainly need	0.896
12.	Students with reading problem have difficulty in	0.816
13.	Attention deficit disorder can be characterized in children if	0.997
14.	Example of Specific learning disabilities is	0.898
15.	Which of the following is not a dimension of Silver organizes Learning Disabilities	0.497
16.	Stuttering is	0.997
17.	Which of the following is a technique used to address stuttering	0.903
18.	Which of the following is an example of an intellectual disability	0.894
19.	Which of the following criteria can be used to define Intellectual disabilities	0.828
20.	Problem related to spelling can be improved by	0.877
21.	Which of the following is developmental disorder	0.895
22.	Percentage of pre-school children who are diagnosed with a phonological disorder of unknown origin is	0.891
23.	Which of the following is NOT a physical cause often associated with Phonological disorder	0.895
24.	Which of the following procedures can be used to identify Down Syndrome pre-natally	0.598
25.	In moderate to severe intellectual impairment in Individuals with Down syndrome	0.910
26.	Students with Learning Disabilities do not have serious problems in	0.946
27.	Children with ADHD often are classified as	0.804
	Overall	0.934

Table 4
Domains of Attitude scale with Cronbach's Alpha

Domains	Total number of items	Cronbach's Alpha
General Attitude about Learning Disabilities	12	0.906
Teaches Attitude in Helping Children with Learning Disabilities	16	0.901
Attitude about Inclusion of Children with Learning Disabilities	12	0.935
Total	40	0.910

The Cronbach's alpha for the attitude scale for this study was 0.88. The Cronbach's alpha for the three dimensions of this study were as follows: General Attitude about Learning Disabilities (0.906), Teaches Attitude in Helping Children with Learning Disabilities (0.901) and Attitude about Inclusion of Children with Learning Disabilities (0.935). The results are included in Table-4

Objective -03 :- To find the relationship between level of awareness with attitude

Table-5
Relationship between variables

Relationship	Level of awareness and attitude of teachers
Correlation (r)	0.69
p value	0.05

Positive correlation was found between level of awareness and attitude of the teachers 0.69 at 0.05 level of significance (Table-5).

Objective 4:- To find out the feasibility

Difficulties faced by the Researcher:-

During pilot study data collection from elementary school teachers at selected schools of District Dholpur Rajasthan, researcher faced following problems:-

1. The respondent don't share their personal information due to fear of cyber crime
2. All teachers were not available at the time data collection due to Covid-19 pandemic

Strategy will be adopted to resolve the above problem while collecting the main study

data collection. They are as follows:-

- 1 Instead of Respondents personal information the researcher will make as sample coding
- 2 Revisited the schools

Discussion: This pilot study was aimed to estimate the reliability coefficient of various questionnaires used in the study; to investigate the level of awareness & attitude of elementary school teachers regarding children with learning disabilities and to calculate the sample size for the main study. The results indicated that the reliability coefficient of level of awareness was 0.93 and 0.95 for the attitude for learning disabilities. This was supported by the findings of Dr. Vrand MN Associate Professor Department of Psychiatric Social Work NIMHANS. Bengaluru - 560029 (2015) reporting the total scale reliability of attitude scale 0.92.

Regarding the hypothesis, relationship between level of awareness and attitude of teachers regarding learning disabilities, a positive correlation was found (0.69).

Conclusion

This pilot study represents that the good level of awareness & favourable attitude of the teachers with learning disabilities will influence the learning. This study recommends that frequent evaluation of teachers & proving the education regarding learning disabilities will more helpful for the teachers while dealing with such children .

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Ethical clearance

It was obtained from, ethical committee of the Desh Bhagat University Mandi Gobindgarh Punjab & District Education Officer (Elementary) Dist-Dholpur, Chief Block Education office Baseri Dist, Dholpur Rajasthan informed consent was taken from principals & respondents.

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